

Information and communication technologies (ICT) are the fuel of the digital society. This article reviews the big challenges to make ICT (more) circular.

Towards circular ICT: From materials to components

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Europe is facing one of the biggest challenges of its history: that of preserving a viable environment for the decades to come. On human consciousness of its environmental impact, Albert Allen Bartlett [1] said: “The greatest shortcoming of the human race is our inability to understand the exponential function”. ICT was, and still is, driven by exponential functions (Moore’s law, ops/Watt, data exchanges volume worldwide,...). However, each exponential has its sustainability limits which are often reached sooner than expected.

In ICT history to date, when those limits are reached, they are overcome by a technology breakthrough. By way of example, there was the CMOS (complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor) technology, a product of laboratory curiosity of the 1980s when bipolar transistor power consumption was too high. New integrated system (multi-core processor) and device (SOI, FinFET,...) architectures entered the market when energy consumption limits were reached by central processing units (CPUs). Today, CMOS is still the cheapest and most reliably power-efficient technology for the development and growth of the internet of things (IoT).

Awareness of the rapid proliferation of wirelessly connected objects around us gives rise to questions and fears among the public. There is a need for more transparency on the environmental footprint of ICT and a need to establish an ambitious roadmap, at research and industrial levels, for moving into a virtuous cycle of eco-innovation.

In this article, we propose pathways to maintain or even reduce global (exponential) use of energy and materials for ICT.

Key insights

- ICT is energy demanding and contributes to approximately 4% of greenhouse gas emissions. Approximately half of the emissions associated with ICT are generated at the production stage.
- ICT is based on a large number of critical materials and Europe imports nearly all of them.
- Recycling of ICT is technically difficult, consumes energy, generates pollution, and is not currently profitable because of the low price of primary raw materials. Only 10-15% of electronics waste is recycled.
- A product-centric economy favours the “produce, consume and waste” vision and thus leads to planned obsolescence of digital objects and infrastructure. A service-centred model would be more in line with the principles of the circular economy.
- The “rebound effect” cancels out the efficiency gains of any ICT system.
- It is time to design differently, to design within limits.

Key recommendations

- Expand the lifetime of devices through better design, both by enhancing the intrinsic durability of components and by adopting a modular approach in which the replacement of faulty or obsolete components is made easy.
- Rethink software and applications to make them less resource consuming (data, energy, hardware) and compatible with still usable hardware. Make software reconfigurable and evolutive.
- Integrate circular economy concepts, eco-design and full life cycle assessment (including fabrication, use and end-of-first-life phases) at the early stage of research and development of new ICT technologies.
- Avoid toxic and substitute critical materials to protect environmental and human health, as well as facilitating the recycling of materials at the end of the device or component life. Use secondary (recycled) materials and use more renewable energy, and develop bio-based and greener chemistry in the ICT industry. This requires enhanced basic and applied research into materials and fabrication processes.
- Draft guidelines and legal policies to enforce supply-chain transparency for all imported and non-imported materials and components.
- Develop new economic models which lead to the decoupling of economic profitability from the depletion of natural resources, for instance the economy of the functionality applied to ICT.

An increasing impact of ICT growth on natural resources

Behind our screens, we have the impression of living in a dematerialized world, where everything is fast, clean, and reconfigurable. The reality is different. The digital society we live in has never been so energy- and material-intensive and this is leading to increasing pressure on natural resources, ecosystems and the climate. Today, ICT is a growing economic activity, similarly to transport, energy production, manufacturing and agriculture. Information and communication technologies consume around 5% of the world's electricity production and are responsible for around 4% of greenhouse gases, a level equivalent to air transport. Our smartphone contains electronic circuits that require more than sixty different materials. We are talking about virtually every element on Mendeleev's periodic table except radioactive materials. At the end of their life, the recycling rate of electronic equipment is very low (less than 15%).

It is extremely difficult to separate the sixty materials that make up electronic circuits.

Umicore, one of the most advanced companies in the field of electronic materials recycling, manages to extract 17 elements out of the 60. Material recovery from obsolete equipment is not profitable given the low cost of raw materials

imported from countries south of the equator. We do not pay for the environmental and social costs. This leads to a double penalty for the Southern countries: they suffer from environmental pollution (loss of biodiversity, pollution of the air and groundwater, etc.) during the extraction of raw materials, as well as receiving 75% of our electronic waste.

Figure 1: Estimation of distribution of the energy consumption of digital technologies for production (45%) and use (55%) Source: The Shift Project, 2018

Towards low-waste production

Efforts are being made to reduce power consumption and industrial waste during the manufacturing of electronic devices and their components. For example, low temperature processes, reduction of heat dissipation in and from the oven, and reduction and recycling of chemicals and water cleaning, are evaluated for each step of the manufacturing of nanoelectronics devices. However, beyond resource efficiency and recycling waste, the transition towards a cost-effective circular economy needs to be implemented and the general design methodologies of materials for sustainable development proposed by Ashby [19] adapted to specific ICT domains such nanoelectronics.

Some companies are beginning to adopt the lifecycle approach including, for example, in the production and recycling of the ultra-pure water needed [2] for the microelectronics industry. There are active research programmes, both on the part of equipment makers and in research labs, seeking to reuse exhausted gas or fluids within the fab [11], and also to develop much more efficient material deposition techniques.

There is still room for improvement and high potential for reduction in use of raw materials. While progress is continually being made towards greener chemistry, this approach is still far from being environmentally friendly and etches away a significant fraction of materials, as well requiring very high consumption of water for rinsing. The reduction of toxic chemicals such as solvents in the microelectronics foundries must be a priority. Tomorrow, bio-based [12] chemicals and materials may be used to reduce significantly the use of solvents and chemicals in lithography, as shown in preliminary results [13]; more research efforts are required. Bio-based materials are also being investigated for use in packaging in the ICT domain.

More circularity between companies must be facilitated by the coherent installation of industrial activities in the same area, thus developing eco-systems in which the by-products or waste from one industry could be the supply material for another.

For instance, the hafnium required in CMOS production is a by-product of ultrapure zirconium used by the nuclear industry and produced mainly in France and the United States [14].

To further reduce the waste of energy and materials, the ICT industry must adopt a holistic approach to developing sustainable products. Several initiatives already exist in the private sector. As an example, we can point out the significant and long-term efforts by STMicroelectronics to evaluate (by lifecycle assessment) the carbon footprint of their microcontrollers [15] and to establish a clear material declaration available online.

To envision a more sustainable future, Europe must:

- Take clear actions to make the ICT supply chain more transparent.
- Make lifecycle assessment and declarations of materials systematic (including for imported products) with shared methodology worldwide.
- Implement a clear and ambitious plan to maximize product lifetime and anticipate its end of life.

This will encourage both research and industry sectors to innovate for the good of everyone.

Looking at minerals

The electronic industry needs a wide variety of minerals. For example, since the 1970s the silicon-based complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) field-effect transistor (FET) has been the mainstream technology for most transistor applications, thus making today's digital economy possible. Over the years, the number of elements exploited in their manufacture has increased greatly (Figure 2), especially since 2000 with the implementation of high-k dielectrics and metal gate stacks which are essential to minimize short-channel effects and gate-leakage current of short transistors (today gate length shorter than 20 nm).

A growing awareness of the limited nature of the supplies of some elements that have specialized and important uses is reflected in the proliferation of terms to describe them and the ores from which they are derived, including 'gateway minerals' and 'critical' and 'endangered' elements. Some countries have adopted policies recognizing the high strategic importance of some of these for their physical and economic security.

Figure 2: Introduction of elements in the manufacture of CMOS transistors: complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) transistors mainly involved silicon, oxygen, boron, phosphorus and integrated circuit interconnections were made of aluminium in the 1980s. There were relatively few changes in the 1990s, but a large diversity of elements was introduced in early 2000 and many integrated circuit interconnections were switched to copper.

In 2010, 14 elements were considered as critical by the European Commission (EC) according to both their strategic importance for future technology and their scarcity, while in 2017 the number rose to 17, including metals (such as tungsten and some rare earth elements), and also other raw materials such as phosphates, natural graphite and magnesite[3].

Modern devices and systems rely heavily on a high degree of control of material properties and a mastery of manufacturing techniques and, to date, the ICT industry has been remarkably successful in fulfilling these needs.

The manufacturing process is a “top-down” or “subtractive” one based on UV photolithography, etching and many sequential, highly organized and efficient steps of chemical and physical treatment of the chip, layer after layer.

Although silicon is abundant on Earth, the sand used to produce high-purity silicon is already being viewed as a scarce commodity due to its multiple additional uses in concrete, asphalt and glass.

Work is being undertaken on substituting or decreasing the use of toxic, hazardous and critical raw materials. For currently crucial elements such as indium, ruthenium, platinum, gallium, arsenic and gold, new technologies and materials are being investigated with a view to replacing them or drastically limiting their use in some critical devices (e.g. in sensors, memories, optoelectronics and spintronics).

Other examples of the move towards sustainable electronics include the avoidance of lead in micro-components like actuators included in cell phones, use of 2D mono-atomic or ultra-thin atomic-deposition layers to reduce the use of some active materials by a factor of up to 106, and use of silicon-based substrates such as silicon-on-insulator (SOI), instead of materials made from combinations of group III and group V elements, for radiofrequency (RF) technologies.

The scaling down of dimensions of high-tech devices in recent decades and the multiplication of materials in the compo-

nents – some of them in extremely small quantities of a few micrograms – are leading to new challenges in recycling. The need for large amounts of power and the use of aggressive acids and solvents can make recycling of such electronics impractical.

Approaches to increasing the sustainability of microelectronic devices must include extending their lifetimes through better design, by both enhancing the intrinsic durability of components and adopting a modular approach in which replacement of faulty or obsolete components is made easy.

These approaches can draw on the experience of, for example, some European microelectronics manufacturers and R&D laboratories (e.g. On-Semi, X-FAB, Infineon, ST-Microelectronics, NXP) that are designing or fabricating highly reliable components for automotive, energy management and security applications.

Challenging the ‘top-down’ or subtractive approach, ‘bottom-up’, additive fabrication processes may offer a new paradigm for ultra-small circuit design. This could involve 3D printing and consist in layer-on-layer depositing of 2D materials such as graphene, molybdenum sulphide and hexagonal boron nitride [4]. Nanomaterials offer potential alternatives to the widely used indium tin oxide transparent conducting layers. Proposed alternatives include a transparent plastic sheet on which nanocarbons have been deposited, or which contains a loose conducting nanomesh [5]. It is expected that technology based on nanostructures will require far fewer raw materials than any traditional approach. However, recycling nanomaterials at the end of the life of the device will bring new, challenging problems [6].

Steps towards the ambitious goal of achieving the sustainability of the material basis of the digital society will require concerted action covering a range of interlocked approaches. These will address the entire lifecycle of not only the digital devices themselves but also the services that support them, paying attention to their energy and environmental footprints

as well as economy and efficiency in the utilization of resources.

Research into substituting critical materials with more abundant ones or which leads to breakthroughs to reduce significantly their use, for instance by localizing active atoms where needed, will open up the path to more responsible electronics.

Waste hierarchies and multiple Rs

The concept of waste hierarchies has become a central feature of the 3R (reduce, reuse, recycle) and circular economy approaches, in which materials recovered across the lifecycle are re-applied at the highest possible level of utility and with minimization of waste or environmental damage. The potential of the approach is evidenced by the virtual disappearance of waste landfilling in, for example, the Netherlands [7].

However, the need to take a comprehensive view of the entire global system of recycling is illustrated by the case of microelectronic devices. Around 50 million tonnes of electronic waste, or e-waste, is thrown away each year. A large amount of e-waste (40% of that produced by Canada, the EU and the United States) is shipped in containers to countries in Africa and Asia, where people manually dismantle the appliances and burn them in the open, producing dangerous levels of hazardous substances which severely impact their health.

Over the last few decades, the number of Rs has grown and at least eleven have been cited in relation to the operation of circular chemistry. Their relevance to the challenge of the sustainability of the material basis of the digital society is outlined in Table 1.

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Table 1: Levels of resource hierarchy and relevance to sustainability of the digital society

Level	Level definition	Explanation and application to sustainability of the digital society
1	Reject	<p>Rejecting use of a material or process, whether to conserve scarce resources, reduce energy demand or avoid serious pollution, is considered the highest hierarchy level. A broad approach to sustainability will require questions such as: “do we really want this component, product or process at all?” and “can this substance be replaced by one that is more available, less toxic, or more readily recyclable?”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU directives restrict the use of harmful substances, such as lead in solders used in microelectronics circuitry. • It has been shown to be possible to replace rare-earth metals used in electronic devices with combinations of more common elements [8]. • Harmful organic solvents can be substituted with more eco-friendly ones [9].
2	Reduce	<p>Overall reduction in the quantities of materials and energy consumed can be achieved with a combination of strategies including product simplification (e.g. fewer materials), miniaturization of the constitutive transistors, interconnects, electrical components, improved battery performance and lower energy consumption, increased product life span and reduced distance for transport.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3D printing and other additive processes are being introduced in microelectronics to lower the consumption of raw materials and chemicals for etching. • Graphene is being explored [16] as a replacement for transparent conductive films such as indium tin oxide widely used in touchscreen applications. • Efforts have been made to replace or at least to reduce the amounts of ‘III-V’ materials such as InP, GaAs, GaN with high carrier mobility, which are used in high frequency devices. Thanks to the silicon-on-insulator technology introduced to the market in 2012, more than 95% of RF switches used in mobile devices are now silicon- and not III-V-based. Furthermore, III-V localization by local wafer bonding (for instance CEA-Leti [17]) or local epitaxial growth (for instance imec [18]), only where this material is needed, drastically reduces the amount used.
3	Reuse	<p>Reuse enables an object to remain in service for a long period of time. The library is a very widely known example.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Second-hand shops are a familiar way of enabling reuse of items for their original purpose, including laptops, tablets, smartphones, and many other electronics appliances. • Leasing of ICT equipment (e.g. smartphones provided on a use/return basis as part of a mobile network contract) can also be a channel for reuse, depending on the approach of the leasing company. For example, nearly all the internet provider companies do not sell their WiFi box to clients but rent them. The company stays responsible for the box. They take care of its maintenance and upgrade. Thanks to this move to the economic model of functionality instead of ownership, the lifetime of each electronics component is greatly extended.
4	Redistribute	<p>Redistribution is also concerned with reusing resources, but involves transport over longer distances – for example, to bring a second-hand product to a new market.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rates of mobile phone usage have risen very steeply in Africa in recent years, with Nigeria providing the biggest African market for second-hand smartphones.
5	Repair	<p>Repairing and maintenance are generally the least resource-intensive solutions to extend the life of devices that are damaged or cease to perform effectively. Unfortunately, however, the way that most ICT devices are manufactured does not facilitate their repair. Moreover, access to spare parts is often impossible or only guaranteed for a short period of time. Once a device needs repair, critical factors are a good diagnosis of the problem and easily removable elements.</p> <p>There is growing interest from both consumers and some producers in repair of ICT devices.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens’ initiatives such as ‘repair cafés’ are flourishing in many countries, providing locations where specialist tools are available and expert advice may be offered by volunteers. Thanks to the internet, there are also several websites which bring people together to form a community for helping each other repair things, for example iFixit. • Consumer pressure for the redesign of electronic products to promote repair rather than disposal of broken items has been growing and has been reflected in the EU’s circular economy approach. • Fairphone, the world’s first ethical modular smartphone on the market, has been designed for a high level of reparability. Most of the spare parts can be ordered online and the product webpage has many tutorials to assist consumers to repair or upgrade their device.

THE RACE FOR SUSTAINABILITY

6	Refurbish	<p>For electronic materials, refurbishment means combining repaired and redistributed products. It may also involve updating a product to current standards. Availability of components and accessibility for repair and replacement are critical.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reconditioned cellular phones are sometimes returned to the market by companies that initially produced them and recovered them after a period of use. In 2019, Fairphone launched its programme “Refurbished phones give valuable resources a new life”. These phones have the same high-quality standards as a brand new Fairphone and the same two-year warranty – but a lower price (half the price of a brand new one).
7	Repurpose	<p>Repurposing is the updating or adaptation of a product such that it can be used to serve a new function or within another context.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are initiatives such as Puzzlephone from which, at the end of a smartphone life, parts can be used in a new context or application such as in a computer. The repurposing of an object will be favoured if retrieval of its functional parts is possible.
8	Remanufacture	<p>Remanufacture is generally a more thorough process of disassembling a product, replacing worn and broken parts with new ones and reassembling it.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An assessment of remanufacturing of end-of-life computers identified the potential to enhance resource conservation and prevent natural resource degradation, and that remanufactured computers could be technically, environmentally, economically and socially feasible if there is an adequate supply of quality cores, involvement of highly skilled workers, incorporation of a standardization process, and the use of advanced machinery.
9	Recycle	<p>As well as the simple reuse of materials, recycling also encompasses the recovery of component materials to act as a feedstock for new material or device production.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electronic scrap comprises a highly complex and heterogeneous group of materials. Only a few precious elements present in integrated circuits are recovered by current recycling techniques because they require a large amount of energy and the use of highly polluting chemicals, while freshly mined minerals are relatively cheap. However, Umicore refines e-scrap containing precious metals such as silver, gold, palladium and copper. • The problem of flame-retardant additives needs to be solved in order to recover plastic components of e-waste. • Better technology is needed to improve the purity of recycled metals such as noble metals used in digital equipment. • More sustainable chemical and biological processes may be applicable to both synthesis and recycling of organic components such as polymers.
10	Recover	<p>Recovery involves retrieving the lowest forms of energy or feedstock for energy production from a material. The actual material is broken down and cannot be recycled further.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a huge number of waste-to-energy plants in the world. Burning waste and particularly e-waste produces, in addition to CO₂, toxic smoke and fine particles which are difficult to prevent from being released into the atmosphere. The efficiency of these waste-to-energy plants and their impacts on human health and the environment remain challenging. • Production of hydrogen as a fuel from printed circuit boards by steam gasification has been examined [10].
11	Return	<p>Most hierarchies call this landfill. However, this stage is more than that – it encompasses the return (sometimes in chemically modified form) not only of solids, but also liquids and gases, back to the environment after use.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More than 70% of e-waste makes its way into landfill, leading to potentially dangerous contamination of groundwater.

It is emphasized that attention to the Rs alone will not solve the problems of waste and resource depletion in the next couple of decades, but will help to extend the timeframe of a transition period during which optimal solutions to sustainable sourcing, production, use and recycling can be developed. In terms of the mining of

the currently required minerals, diversified approaches must be developed during this transition period. These include at least three complementary avenues:

1. Develop further mining of current mine waste in order to use the maximum amount possible of the extracted rocks, minerals and chemical elements.

This will require thorough knowledge of each deposit, information/teaching to mining companies and, where possible, new regulations.

2. Encourage refining of by-products in the mining of the main deposits of ores (i.e. low-abundance chemical elements associated with a much more abundant

one). For example, potentially valuable levels of gallium and scandium are associated with ores of aluminium. Similarly, useful quantities of copper, antimony, silver, arsenic and tellurium may be recovered from gold deposits. However, at the same time, there is a need to develop independent supplies of technologically important minerals, beyond their ‘companionality’ as a by-product of one or more host metals from geologic ores, to ensure reliability of supplies.

- Promote tolerance of new, responsible mining of metals in countries or regions which have become averse to mining. This will require education, with frank and balanced information provision and discussion that engages civil society, scientists and engineers, government and the media. The discussions must include assessment of the true price of raw materials, including the ethical and environmental prices (which is not the case at the moment), and would lead to increased costs of raw material in the coming years, with concomitant increased costs of the associated products. Taking account of the “true” price would, in turn, help engender a redefining and reordering of priorities for production and consumption.

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References

- Al Bartlett, <https://www.albartlett.org/>
- W. Den, C.-H. Chen, Y.-C. Luo. “Revisiting the water-use efficiency performance for microelectronics manufacturing facilities: Using Taiwan’s Science Parks as a case study”. *Water-Energy Nexus* 1 (2018) 116-133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wen.2018.12.002>.
- “List of Critical Raw Materials for the EU”. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on the 2017 European Commission, Brussels, COM/2017/0490 final, 2017. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52017DC0490> (accessed 29 August 2020).
- X. Ling, Y. Lin, Q. Ma, Z. Wang, Y. Song, L. Yu, S. Huang, W. Fang, X. Zhang, A.L. Hsu, Y. Bie, Y. Lee, Y. Zhu, L. Wu, J. Li, P. Jarillo-Herrero, M. Dresselhaus, T. Palacios, J. Kong. “Parallel stitching of 2D materials”. *Adv. Mater.* 28 (2016) 2322-2329. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201505070>.
- A. Khan, S. Lee, T. Jang, Z. Xiong, C. Zhang, J. Tang, L.J. Guo, W.D. Li. “High-performance flexible transparent electrode with an embedded metal mesh fabricated by cost-effective solution process”. *Small* 12(22) (2016) 3021-3030. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.201600309>.
- S.A. Younis, E.M. El-Fawal, “P. Serp. Nano-wastes and the environment: Potential challenges and opportunities of nano-waste management paradigm for greener nanotechnologies”, in: C. Hussain (Ed.), *Handbook of Environmental Materials Management*. Springer, Cham, 2018. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-58538-3_53-1.
- A. Lansink. “Challenging changes – Connecting waste hierarchy and circular economy”. LEA, Nijmegen ISBN/EAN 978-90-821783-5-7, 2017. <https://www.challengingchanges.org/the-book/> (accessed 29 August 2020).
- M. Irving. “Common element combos could replace rare-Earth metals in electronics”. *New Atlas* 5 July 2019. <https://newatlas.com/common-elements-replace-rare-earth-metals-electronics/60447/> (accessed 29 August 2020).
- F. Pena-Pereira, A. Kloskowski, J. Namieśnik. “Perspectives on the replacement of harmful organic solvents in analytical methodologies: a framework toward the implementation of a generation of eco-friendly alternatives”. *Green Chemistry* 17 (2015) 3687-3705. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5GC00611B>.
- J.A. Salbidegoitia, E.G. Fuentes-Ordóñez, M.P. González-Marcos, J.R. González-Velasco, T.K. Bhaskar. “Steam gasification of printed circuit board from e-waste: Effect of coexisting nickel to hydrogen production”. *Fuel Processing Technol.* 133 (2015) 69-74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2015.01.006>.
- “CVD-semens monosilane reactor process with complete utilization of feed gases and total recycle”, patent US 8,657,958 B2, 2014
- M. Caillau et al, “Sub-micron lines patterning into silica using water developable chitosan bioresist films for eco-friendly positive tone e-beam and UV lithography”, *SPIE Advanced Lithography*, 2018, San Jose, California
- Mathieu Caillau, Pierre Crémillieu, Emmanuelle Laurenceau, Yann Chevolot and Jean-Louis Leclercq, “Fifty nanometer lines patterned into silica using water developable chitosan bioresist and electron beam lithography”, <https://doi.org/10.1116/1.4996870>
- Framatome, “Fuel Business Unit Jarrie”, <https://www.framatome.com/EN/businessnews-142/framatome-fuel-business-unit—jarrie.html>
- ST, “Footprint of a Microcontroller”, https://www.st.com/content/st_com/en/about/st_approach_to_sustainability/sustainability-priorities/sustainable-technology/eco-design/footprint-of-a-microcontroller.html
- Dexter Johnston, “The Market for Nanomaterial Solutions for ITO Replacement Gets Crowded”, <https://spectrum.ieee.org/nanoclast/semiconductors/nanotechnology/nanomaterial-solutions-for-ito-replacement-gets-crowded>
- Bertrand Szlag, Karim Hassan, Laetitia Adelmini, Elodie Ghegin, Philippe Rodriguez, Fabrice Nemouchi, Pierre Brianceau, Elisa Vermande, Antoine Schembri, David Carrara, Pierrick Cavalié, Florent Franchin, Christophe Jany, Segolene Olivier, “Hybrid III–V/Silicon Technology for Laser Integration on a 200-mm Fully CMOS-Compatible Silicon Photonics Platform”, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSTQE.2019.2904445>
- Alan Y. Liu, John Bowers. “Photonic Integration With Epitaxial III–V on Silicon” <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSTQE.2018.2854542>
- Ashby, “M. Materials and Sustainable Development”. Butterworth-Heinemann (2015). <https://www.elsevier.com/books/materials-and-sustainable-development/ashby/978-0-08-100176-9> (accessed 29 August 2020).

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